

Lecture2:

- We could know which neuron in the model responsible for which class, by using the one-hot vector.
 - The one hot vector is a vector of all zeros and a single one in the right class. You can use it when you have a single animal per picture and in this case the activation function used is “softmax”.
 - You can do multiclass regression using “one-hot vector” or even better you can use “multiple-hot vector” and it’s better because it enables you to classify images with objects from two classes.
 - Hidden layers of the network do different jobs such as the first one detect edges, the second detect corners, the third start to have a shallow understanding of the image and so on until the image get classified.
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- First step when building a model is to choose the amount of the data you want to work on, so for a simple (0,1) classifier 10,000 images could be enough. In this case you can split (80-20%).
 - When the data is big like 1,000,000 you could split (98% training – 2% test).
 - You must balance between the classes so you do not have so many of one class and so little from the other. Must be almost 50-50. And balanced datasets means have no bias.
 - The input will be the pixel image, with resolution as low as you can that enable you to achieve good results. By running the model multiple times on different sized images or by comparing to human performance (means choose the smallest image humans can classify perfectly).
 - For the day’n night model the last activation function is “sigmoid”. Because sigmoid is used for binary classification while “softmax” for multiclass classification.
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- In face verification task it does not work to compare the images pixel-to-pixel, so instead we pass the first image into a deep network and get a vector then pass the second image into the same deep network and get a vector for the second image too, then compare the two vectors the result should satisfy some threshold, which will indicate the class of the image. And getting the right deep network depends on the loss function design.
 - The learning process: you feed the model an image (Anchor) and a (positive) image which is of the same class as the anchor and a (Negative) image which is for another class, and the model will give us three vectors one to each image, then calculate the loss of each vector, then the gradient and feed them back to the model as parameters so the model will have a better understanding of what it is looking for. And that does not affect the weights.
 - L-means algorithm is a clustering algorithm, where you can give it a group of pictures and it will make clusters of similar pictures.
 - The loss function of this task is the “L2 difference between the anchor and the positive minus the L2 difference between the anchor and the negative” and it makes sense because we want to maximize the positive term which is the first one and to minimize the second one which is the one after the minus sign.

- Art generation: to generate a picture with a different style (neural style transfer), you feed the model your image (content image) and a second one (style image) (a famous painting for example) and the model will give an image that is a mix between the two.
- The architecture of this image is a network trained on "imagenet" and we can get the contents (edges) of the content image and the style (all the features) of the style image by going back to the layers of the model.
- So here we are not training to learn parameters, but in fact we are learning an image, and we do not care about it's class.
- Start with a white noise to train the model and that is to avoid bias for one of the images.

- When working on speech recognition we use sound clips for training with the same sample rate of the speech, and the model will label all the speech that does not contain the trigger word with zeros and when the trigger is said it's labeled with one.
- The activation function should be sigmoid (sequential) and the architecture will have to be RNN.
- For training you collect a positive word, negative words, background noise databases and train the model to recognize the positive. Instead of recording sound clips and labeling them.
- Sometimes your model does not work because it has the wrong architecture, and you need to ask an expert to know the right layers and their connection.

- The loss function of YOLO model is the most beautiful loss function.

Lecture 3

- Steps of an ML project:
 - o Select a problem (supervised learning or GAN) such as speech recognition, where your input is an audio clip and the model will find the trigger word in it.
 - o Get data
 - o Design model
 - o Train model
 - o Test model
 - o QA
 - o Deploy
 - o Maintain

- Project selection criteria (Select a problem):
 - o Interest: means you should work on a project that is interesting to you.
 - o Data: availability of data.

- Domain knowledge: if you have a background in a certain science, it will be interesting to build a project which is an application in that science and use your knowledge in.
 - Utility: such as money or equipment.
 - Feasibility: means it has to be attainable, affordable and possible.
- Engineering scrum: is taking the Fibonacci series to estimate how long the project will take. And Fibonacci series is (1,2,3,5,8,13....) where each number is the summation of the previous two.
 - You would probably spend 1 or 2 days on collecting data, and recommended less than a week. But getting the data, building a model and iterating is how machine learning projects goes.
 - When designing a model keep clear notes on experiments run.
 - Deployment: reading “war stories” might help when deploying a model.
 - For example, when building a (voice activity detector) you can use:
 - Non-ML: based model detects (voice > ϵ)
 - Train a small neural network on human speech
 - The maintenance of the model is changing the data or adding new data according to the changes in the world. For example: a neural network built to work in California will not do as good working with Texas traffic lights. So, it’s simply means updating the model.
 - As a maintenance application: is the speech recognition such as amazon echo, where the model and the data are in the cloud but the edge device is the one using and gathering the data, so both will be used when updating the model.

Lecture4

Attacking NN with adversarial examples:

- To attack the network with adversarial examples, we first need to get a misclassified image. And we could get that image using “neural style transfer”.
- Introduce the loss function
- Optimize the image

Defense against adversarial examples:

- Types of attacks
 - Non-targeted attacks
 - Targeted attacks

- Knowledge of the attacker
 - o White-box attacks: when you have access to a network
 - o Black-box attacks: you don't have access to the network, i.e., parameters, layers...etc.

Solutions: (against the attacks)

- Create a SafetyNet. I.e., create an adversarial example on a similar purpose network and use that same example on the targeted network. It's called transferability
- Train on correctly labelled adversarial examples, i.e., create a dataset of adversarial examples and train the network on them
- Adversarial training, i.e., include adversarial examples in your training set. AND/OR Logit training.

Why are neural networks vulnerable to adversarial examples.

- The cause of the adversarial examples is the linear part of the network.
- The question of the adversarial examples is: can we find an input x^* that is close to x but radically changes the output of the network?
- Insights from an example in the lecture:
 - o If w is large then x^* does not equal x .
 - o As x grow in dimension the change in \bar{y} will increase, in other words, if x is close to x^* and the bigger the dimension of x the bigger the change in \bar{y} will be. So, the bigger the dimensions of the image the more likely it will be adversarial.
- "fast gradient sign method" is a fast way to generate an adversarial example
- All the research is heading towards linearizing the neural networks, because it is faster to train.

When we apply the chain rule there is a middle term that is (dz) we want to enlarge because that will result the ability to train the parameters of the network and without this gradient we will not be able to train the network.

GANs:

- The goal of gans is to collect lots of data and use it to train a model to generate even more data.
- The intuition of gans is that: there is a lot of images data in the world and a limited number of parameters in the model.
- To get the gan to function correctly we need to make the probability distribution of the generated data equal to the probability distribution of the original dataset.
- To start building a GAN first thing we initialize a generator with a set of scalar numbers for it to generate a noise image.
- We bring a real-world dataset and find its probability distribution.

- Define another network (Discriminator) that will find if the input image was real world or something else.
- And then we input to the discriminator images from the real-world dataset and others from the generator, and it has to give correct binary classification,
- Now we get the gradients from the discriminator as back propagation to feed them into the discriminator as well as the generator network.
- And you take the gradient back to the generator input as well because the generator input and the discriminator input are dependent.
- In the training process we want to minimize:
 - o The cost of the discriminator: with cost function to label real data as 1 and generated data as 0.
 - o The cost of the generator: the cost function of the generator is the opposite of the discriminator cost function $J^{(G)} = -J^{(D)}$ which means it is trying to fool the discriminator

A cycle GAN:

Is about having two generators and two discriminators and generating images on two sides back and forth, i.e., a horse2zebra GAN is about generating horse images from zebra images and zebra images from horse images.

To evaluate GANs:

- Human annotators.
- Inception score (IS).
- Fréchet inception distance (FID).

Lecture 5

- AI in healthcare: looking at the healthcare process we could ask a few questions:
 - o Descriptive: What happened?
 - o Diagnostic: Why did it happen?
 - o Predictive: What will happen?
 - o Prescriptive: What should we do?
- Paradigm shift in machine learning:
 - o In machine learning the feature extraction and classification are two separate processes, while in deep learning the feature extraction and classification happens as a single process.
- AI in healthcare research:
 - o Multiple types of problems are being researched for example:
 - 1D problem: ECG, when we build a neural network to process the data of it, it will be working on a 1D time variable data. Using ResNet for example where you add a shortcut across each block to the next block.

- 2D problem: Chest X-Ray, which could be processed with CheXRay convolutional network, and it's built on the DenseNet architecture, which means connecting all the blocks to each other by shortcut connections.
- In case of a 2D problem and we do not have a "ground truth" for a comparison between a radiologist and a CheXRay model, we can take an average for a group of radiologists and the model and compare the model and expert radiologist to that average.
 - 3D problem: MR Scans, for example knee MR scans, where you need to have pictures for the image from 3 sides to construct the knee view.
- You and AI in healthcare: one way is to look at it is by considering the "MURA" dataset and build your own model on it/
- Segmentation: is assigning a value class to each pixel in the image. And creating a "mask" image with the segmentation values.
- Data augmentation could help the model to perform better, but in some cases, it could hurt the model such as when using FlowNet to detect the speed of a car, if you use "stretching" as an augmentation it will make it harder to calculate the speed of the car, and the same if you use "flip" on a character recognition model.
- Another hyperparameter is the number of layers that you could consider to not train from the pretrained images in transfer learning.

Lecture 6

- When working on research, especially when you are not experienced with the field of the research, it is recommended to find three to five papers and skim them then choose one or two to read in greater detail, then do that repeatedly until you have the required knowledge.
- When reading a paper and you do not understand it, contact the authors and ask them for an explanation. you will have a 50 percent chance to get a response, and do not bother people unless you have done your homework
- It is advised that you do not work on data augmentation unless that you have verified that you have a working model with a high variance problem.
- When working on a speech recognition problem, you can record sound for a certain length then from that sound you can create clips of a smaller length, and use it as a dataset. By that you have turned a sequence recognition problem into a binary classification problem, for example, use the dataset for a trigger word recognition like Alexa by amazon
- To make your trigger recognition system more robust you can take a sample of the background noise in your home and synthesize the noise and the trigger word for the model to train on

- Ways to collect a dataset:
 - o Run across the area and take images or record the audio you like
 - o Download the data online
 - o Use amazon mechanical turk.

Lecture 7

The lecture is about interpreting the output of the network and finding whether it is actually looking at the correct object when classifying, and that gives a more trustable network.

- Ways to interpret neural networks output:
 - o With saliency maps
 - o With occlusion sensitivity
 - o With class activation maps (global average pooling)
- Ways to visualize neural networks from the inside:
 - o With gradient ascent (class model visualization)
 - o With dataset search
 - o The deconvolution and it's applications
- With saliency maps we take the derivative of the score one step before the softmax which will show the focus of the network, and the same layer output could be used for segmentation
- When using sensitivity occlusion, we take an image and cover a square of it and check the score map and see whether the covered square has affected the correct object score and do that for the whole image one square at a time and finally the squares that affect the object score are the ones where the object is located.
- The idea of class activation maps is to show that a network is good in localization even if they are trained only on image level labels, so for example YOLOv2 is trained on huge amounts of data as a classification model, and when it gained a good localization ability, it got fine-tuned and retrained on object recognition data. and to do that with a classification network you can just change the flatten layer with a global average pooling layer and visualize the feature maps and the weight of the final layers.
- When using class model visualization, what we do is to back propagate the image in the network using gradient ascent to find what the network was looking at by visualizing the result
- To visualize the nn from the inside using dataset search, we take a feature map and visualize it then pass all the dataset examples through the network and look which training example activated the feature map the most, and judge what the map is looking at.
- Deconvolution, it gets used by taking an activation from the network and run it through another network equal to the reverse of the convolutional neural network, and at the end of this

deconvolution path we can see in the result the area that most activated the layer, and the reverse network consist of many layers, some are:

- Check the lecture for all the matrices and how the deconvolution layer works.
- And as a result, we can change the convolution to become deconvolution by just doing the following:
 - Flipping the weight.
 - Divide the stride by two.
 - Inserting zeros, according to the sub-pixel convolution method.
- Note, the maxpool is not good in deconvolution because you will lose all the other cells and keep only the maximum value one when maxpooling. So we can use switches to help with deconv of maxpool
- To take the backward of the ReLU layer in back prop we need to have switches, but in deconv we apply the ReLU function on the map received

Lecture 8

- A lot of PhD students learn by osmosis, which means when they see other students doing something they pick it up.
- To study a certain subject, through research papers, suggested to follow the steps:
 - Compile a list of papers (arxiv, GitHub repos, blog posts).
 - Skip around the list, by removing some, reading some deeply and skimming other and adding more from the citations. To have basic understanding or implement some algorithm reading (5-20) will be enough, while (50-100) papers give you a very good understanding.
- **How to** read a paper:
 - The bad way is to go from the first word to the last.
 - Instead:
 - Take multiple passes through the paper.
 - Read the title, abstract, and the figures.
 - Read the intro, conclusions, figures, and skim the rest, but always skip the “related work” section.
 - Read the whole paper but skim the math
 - Read the whole paper but skip the parts that do not make sense, because researchers so many times publish things and they do not know that they are not important.
 - Usually, 20-60 mins will be enough to read a paper
- **Sources** of papers:
 - Twitter. @KianKatan , @AndrewNg
 - ML subreddit

- NIPS / ICML / ICLR (machine learning conferences)
 - Friends and colleges
 - Arxiv-sanity.com
- Reading **math** in papers:
 - Rederive from scratch, PhD students do it a lot. Which will enable you to derive your own new math for your research.
- Papers **code**:
 - Download and run the open-source code.
 - Reimplement from scratch.
- Steady reading works, but not short bursts.

- Career advice:
 - Get a job at a company or startup
 - Or do a PhD
 - In any case of the above, do something important.
- How to get a position, what the recruiters want:
 - Skills (ML, Coding).
 - Meaningful work:
 - Can do work
 - Be a “T” shaped professional, which means learn about a wide variety of things and do a project or research or some other important work in a certain field and go more specific in it. And to build the “T”:
 - For the horizontal part it is right to do course work and reading.
 - The vertical part gets developed by building a relevant project.
 - Don’t learn everything so good just learn about everything and do one thing so great, and don’t jump to work and specialize before learning about many things and understanding the big picture
 - Do one or two great projects, not many small ones, because complexity matters.

- Saturday morning problem: a problem you will have for the rest of your life. The choice you make will not show a short-term reward but in the long term it could mean a lot of work or a lot of wasted time. So, you may do one of the following:
 - Read a paper
 - Work on research
 - Work on open source
 - Watch TV, Andrew and his wife do not own a TV.
- Selecting a job:
 - Work with great people and projects
 - Focus on the team you interact with (10-30 persons)
 - Your manager
 - NOT the brand
- Do not waste years of your life in boring jobs

Lecture 9

- The motivation for studying the deep reinforcement learning is because its performance is better than humans is so many tasks such as games like alpha Go
- For example, trying to play Go using the classic supervised learning will not result an algorithm with a better performance than humans because it will be trained on expert human play moves dataset, and there will be too many states in the game to compute, and it is likely that it will not generalize.
- Classic convolutional networks for supervised learning will not work because the game is about STRATEGY not PATTERN finding.
- Reinforcement learning is about automatically learning to make good sequences of decision.
- Some applications are:
 - o Robotics
 - o Games
 - o Advertisement
- To work on a problem of RL:
 - o Refine the problem and the goal of the program
 - o Define the number of states.
 - o Define the types of states (start, end, normal)
 - o Possible actions
 - o Any additional rules
 - o Define the long-term return (discounted reward is best which is the final reward subtracted from it the steps been taken to get it)
 - o What do we want the algorithm to learn, probably the optimal state action
 - o How to build the algorithm:
 - Build a tree
 - Calculate the long-term discounted reward using Bellman equation
- Now when the tree gets too big it will become hard to calculate all the states and actions, so it is best to use deep learning. And that comes by substituting the states table (states tree) by a deep learning neural network.
- What the neural network does: is taking a state as input and giving an action as output, and here it needs a loss function of a regression problem not classification.
- How the q-learning process works is by the following:
 - o First you need to know that the labels are moving, not defined like other deep learning problems also, you only train on what you have explored and do the following.
 - o We define a label to be the best guess of what would be the best q-function that we have according to the Bellman equation
 - o Compute the loss of where the q-function is right now.
 - o Back propagate so that the loss function gets closer to our best guess
 - o Make a better guess, and make it fixed then repeat
 - o If you have a terminal state, then just output your guess

- When we train in supervised learning, we repeat looking on the data for as many times as the epochs, while in reinforcement learning there are places, we never go to, and we repeat nothing.
- So, using experience replay has two advantages and what it is can be called exploitation, and it takes the exploration place.
- To know when to explore and when to exploit we add a hyperparameter that will decide when to do this and when to do that, and it will decide to explore with 5% probability and exploit with 95% probability.
- Using the human knowledge in the loop would help a lot and that is because it will give the machine a big push ahead
- Still not really understanding reinforcement learning.

Lecture 10

Conversational assistants (Chatbots):

- You start by analyzing the sentence to detect the “intent” (what the sentence is asking for) and then you get the “Slots” (what are the key meaningful words mentioned in the sentence) if the required slots are not mentioned then ask for them.
- Now to evaluate the performance of the chatbot, we can use amazon mechanical turk